
SMART GRID INTEGRATION AND ENERGY MANAGEMENT IN IBOM POWER COMPANY, IKOT ABASI, AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

Smart grid technologies are essential for modernising outdated electrical infrastructure and play a critical role in developing a future-ready, resilient, and sustainable power system, particularly in growing economies like Nigeria. This study investigates the impact of smart grid integration on energy management at Ibom Power Company, located in Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State, with a focus on advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), renewable energy sources, and demand response systems. A survey research design was adopted, targeting a population of 198 employees at Ibom Power Company Limited. A sample size of 131 respondents was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's sample size determination table. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analysed using multiple regression analysis. The results revealed that advanced metering infrastructure, renewable energy sources, and demand response systems collectively have a significant influence on the company's energy management practices ($p < 0.05$). Based on these findings, the study concluded that smart grid integration, measured through advanced metering infrastructure deployment, renewable energy adoption, and demand response mechanisms, significantly enhances energy management. The study recommended that the company fully implement and integrate advanced metering infrastructure across both operational and customer networks to improve efficiency in energy generation, distribution, and consumption. It should also strategically incorporate renewable energy sources, particularly solar and biomass into its power generation portfolio to enhance energy management, reduce reliance on gas-fired systems, and improve energy security. Additionally, the integration of a demand response system as a core component of its energy management strategy is advised to boost grid reliability, reduce peak load pressures, and optimise operational efficiency.

Keyword: Smart Grid Technologies, Advanced Metering Infrastructure, Renewable Energy Sources, Demand Response Systems and Energy Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's energy sector faces considerable challenges in management, distribution, and sustainability. With accelerating urbanisation and economic growth, the demand for a dependable and stable electricity supply has significantly increased. The Ibom Power Company Limited (IPC), one of Nigeria's pioneering independent power producers, plays a vital role in addressing these challenges. However, it continues to grapple with persistent inefficiencies, grid instability, and high transmission losses. These enduring issues have prompted growing interest in the adoption of modern technologies, particularly Smart Grid (SG) systems, to improve the efficiency of energy distribution and management.

Smart grid technologies refer to modernised electrical systems that utilise advanced digital communication, automation, and sensing to monitor and manage electricity networks. These innovations enhance the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of electricity generation, transmission, and consumption (Farooq & Zahoor, 2015). The integration of smart grid systems has shown considerable promise in addressing energy sector challenges through improved demand response, increased grid resilience, and better management of distributed energy resources (Mishra et al., 2022; Bakare et al., 2023). In addition, smart grids support the integration of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar, which are essential for diversifying the energy mix and reducing carbon emissions over time (Meng, 2023). Key components of smart grid systems include advanced metering infrastructure, renewable energy integration, and demand response programmes. Together, these elements contribute to a more sustainable and stable power supply.

A central feature of smart grid infrastructure is Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), which consists of smart meters, communication networks, and data management systems. AMI enables utility providers to monitor and regulate electricity usage more effectively. It allows for two-way communication between utilities and consumers, facilitating real-time data collection, system monitoring, and energy usage analysis (Phing et al., 2023). Similarly, renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydropower are crucial for promoting sustainable development and lowering greenhouse gas emissions. Technological advancements in solar and wind energy are making these options increasingly viable, while hydropower remains a significant contributor despite environmental concerns (Agbakwuru et al., 2024). Additionally, demand response systems encourage consumers to reduce electricity consumption during peak periods. This helps to enhance grid reliability and supports the integration of renewable energy sources (Tahir et al., 2018).

Despite the potential of smart grid technologies, developing countries encounter substantial barriers to implementation. In Nigeria, these include outdated infrastructure, high transmission losses, and limited access to electricity (Somepalli, 2024; Otuoze et al., 2017). Other obstacles include deferred maintenance, obsolete equipment, shortages in electricity supply, corruption, high initial investment costs, a shortage of skilled personnel, weak regulatory frameworks, and institutional resistance to change. These factors present specific challenges for the development of smart grid systems in Nigeria and in Akwa Ibom State (Dahunsi et al., 2022; Somepalli, 2024).

Nonetheless, the use of smart grid technologies could significantly enhance the energy management and operational efficiency of the Ibom Power Company Limited. Given the availability of abundant local energy resources, including natural gas and renewable energy potential, Akwa Ibom State stands to gain from the implementation of modern grid management systems (Abere et al., 2022). Smart grids can provide IPC with real-time data on

electricity consumption, improve load forecasting, reduce power outages, and minimise losses caused by inefficiencies and illegal connections. A more reliable power supply would also support local economic development by fostering industrial growth, which is a key driver of regional prosperity (Nneze et al., 2024).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The rapid advancement of smart grid technologies has significantly reshaped the way electricity is generated, distributed and consumed. However, incorporating these modern technologies into traditional energy systems presents considerable challenges, particularly for Ibom Power Company Limited. The company's operations, especially within Akwa Ibom State, frequently encounter obstacles in monitoring and optimising energy usage, maintaining grid reliability and achieving long-term sustainability.

Smart grids hold substantial promise in enhancing efficiency, lowering operational costs and supporting the integration of renewable energy sources. However, a number of barriers continue to impede their full-scale implementation. These challenges include inadequate infrastructure, limited capacity for data analytics and the high upfront costs associated with adopting smart grid technologies.

In light of the increasing complexity of energy management, it is essential for Ibom Power Company Limited to embrace advanced technologies such as demand response systems, renewable energy sources and Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI). These innovations have the potential to greatly improve the efficiency, reliability and sustainability of the company's operations.

Although extensive research in engineering, computer science and related disciplines has explored the impact of smart grid technologies, there remains a noticeable gap in the literature concerning the managerial perspective, especially how the integration of smart grids can enhance energy management. This gap is especially apparent in the operational context of Ibom Power Company Limited within Akwa Ibom State.

To address this issue, the present study examined the impact of integrating smart grid technologies on the energy management of Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study aimed to:

- i. assess the effect of advanced metering infrastructure on energy management in Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. evaluate the effect renewable energy sources on energy management in the Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. investigate the influence of demand response systems on energy management in Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State.

The following hypotheses were proposed:

- i. **H₀₁:** Advanced metering infrastructure has no significant effect on energy management in Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State
- ii. **H₀₂:** Renewable energy sources do not play a significant role in energy management in Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State

- iii. **H₀₃:** Demand response systems have no significant effect on energy management in Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Smart Grid Technologies

Smart grid technologies represent a significant transformation in electrical power systems, combining improved communication and control mechanisms to enhance efficiency, reliability, and sustainability. A smart grid is an advanced electrical grid that uses digital communication technology, sensors, and automation to monitor, predict, and efficiently manage the generation, distribution, and consumption of electricity. By integrating these technologies, smart grids foster environmental sustainability and lower carbon emissions through the incorporation of renewable energy sources (Karduri *et al.*, 2023; Kiasari *et al.*, 2024).

Notably, there is a strong interplay between smart cities and smart grids. Smart grids form the foundation of smart cities, enabling intelligent energy management that promotes urban development. This integration improves air quality and reduces carbon emissions by incorporating renewable energy sources and efficient energy delivery (Farmanbar *et al.*, 2019).

An essential component in optimising smart grid operations is artificial intelligence (AI). AI improves load forecasting accuracy, optimises power distribution, and detects system anomalies, resulting in more dependable and efficient energy systems. This technical development ensures that energy supply matches demand dynamically, responding to variations in real time.

The integration of distributed energy resources (DERs), such as solar and wind power, enhances smart grid resilience and sustainability and enables customers to create and manage their own energy, minimising dependency on centralised power plants and encouraging energy independence. This decentralisation results in a more robust and adaptable energy infrastructure (Bose, B.K., 2017).

The combination of smart grid technology, artificial intelligence, and distributed energy resources creates a synergy that improves energy system efficiency, reliability, and long-term sustainability. This collaboration not only promotes smart city development but also helps to preserve the environment and increase energy resilience (Arévalo and Jurado, 2024).

2.1.2 Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI)

Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) is a combination of smart meters, communication networks, and data management systems designed to monitor and control energy consumption. It enhances the accuracy of data collection and provides real-time feedback, leading to more efficient utility management (Ungurean & Găitan, 2024; Phing *et al.*, 2024). This technology facilitates the implementation of price-based demand response systems, enabling consumers to reduce their electricity bills while assisting utilities in managing peak demand and lowering carbon emissions.

The integration of AMI with smart grids is particularly valuable in addressing challenges associated with the increasing use of distributed energy resources and electric

vehicles (Chen *et al.*, 2023). AMI also provides significant economic benefits to electricity providers. Its deployment can reduce operational costs and increase efficiency (Biswas *et al.*, 2013; Engelen & Collins, 2014), allowing utilities to streamline operations and optimise resource management.

Furthermore, the synergistic effects of AMI technology result in both operational efficiencies and substantial environmental benefits. By enabling more precise monitoring and control of energy consumption, AMI contributes to waste reduction and supports sustainability goals. These advantages benefit both consumers and energy providers, fostering a more efficient and environmentally friendly energy ecosystem.

However, the use of AMI data raises concerns regarding privacy and cybersecurity, which must be effectively addressed to ensure the successful implementation of these technologies in smart grid environments (Chen *et al.*, 2023).

2.1.3 Renewable energy sources

Renewable energy, derived from natural resources such as sunlight, wind, water, hydro, and hydrogen, is rapidly transforming the global energy landscape by offering sustainable alternatives to fossil fuels (Phanindra *et al.*, 2024; Cui, 2025). Although challenges such as intermittency, high upfront costs, and grid integration persist, renewable sources are projected to account for 42% of global electricity generation by 2028 (Swadi *et al.*, 2024). The transition to renewables not only significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions but also brings economic advantages, including job creation and sustainable development (Swadi *et al.*, 2024). However, integrating renewable energy into existing power systems poses substantial challenges, particularly in areas such as energy storage, grid stability, and power quality (Nzeanorue and Okpala, 2024). Tackling these issues is essential to ensuring a secure and reliable energy future.

2.1.4 Demand Response Systems

Demand response (DR) systems are essential for balancing energy supply and demand in smart grids. These systems encourage users to change their energy consumption habits through a variety of programs and pricing approaches (Vardakas *et al.*, 2015). Real-time pricing, load shifting, and demand-side flexibility are examples of demand response measures that can lower peak demand and increase grid stability (Deng *et al.*, 2015). DR is implemented using mathematical models, optimisation algorithms, and sophisticated technologies like smart meters and the Internet of Things (Stanelytè *et al.*, 2022). DR management helps to integrate renewable energy sources (RES) into the grid by resolving issues such as supply-demand balance and grid stability (Saravanan *et al.*, 2024). Consumer involvement, competitive pricing, and the use of smart energy solutions are necessary for DR systems to be effective. As the energy industry develops, DR remains crucial for building a more flexible, effective, and sustainable energy system (Stanelytè *et al.*, 2022; Saravanan *et al.*, 2024).

2.1.5 Energy Management

Energy management within smart grids incorporates advanced technologies to enhance both efficiency and reliability. A central component is the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), which enables real-time monitoring of energy consumption via smart meters. This facilitates accurate billing and effective load management. AMI also supports Demand Response (DR) programmes, which incentivise consumers to adjust their energy

usage during peak periods, thereby helping to balance grid demand and reduce operational costs.

The integration of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), such as solar panels and wind turbines, introduces variability into the grid (Kiliç, 2024). Smart grids address this challenge through the use of predictive analytics and dynamic load management, which forecast energy production and consumption to optimise the balance between supply and demand. Additionally, the deployment of Energy Storage Systems (ESS) allows for the storage of surplus energy, thereby ensuring a stable supply despite the intermittent nature of renewable sources (Balaji, 2024).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) further enhance energy management capabilities. AI algorithms predict energy demand, detect system anomalies, and enable proactive maintenance, leading to more efficient grid operations. IoT-enabled devices, including smart appliances and sensors, support dynamic load management and consumer engagement, allowing users to monitor and adjust their energy usage. This not only results in cost savings but also contributes to improved grid stability (Balasubramanian and Singh, 2023; Kiliç *et al.*, 2024).

By integrating renewable energy sources and lowering carbon emissions, smart grids contribute to environmental sustainability while improving operational efficiency. Furthermore, ongoing developments in this field address critical issues such as cybersecurity and interoperability, ultimately supporting the seamless integration of renewables into modern energy systems (Kumar and Patra, 2020).

2.2 Theoretically Framework

This study is anchored in Fred Davis's (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), a widely recognised framework for understanding how users adopt and engage with new technologies. TAM identifies two key determinants of technology adoption: perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU). These concepts are particularly relevant when examining the adoption of smart grid technology, as PU is often linked to perceived benefits such as enhanced energy efficiency, cost savings, and system reliability (Park *et al.*, 2012). In this context, PEOU refers to how straightforward and user-friendly smart grid solutions are for end-users to operate and implement.

Users' willingness to adopt such technologies is shaped by both the perceived benefits and the simplicity of interaction. The relative importance of PU and PEOU may vary depending on the nature and complexity of the task at hand (Gefen & Straub, 2000), highlighting the need for tailored deployment strategies. In addition to individual perceptions, the application of TAM to smart grids also considers broader contextual factors such as infrastructure readiness, user awareness, and external influences including government support and incentives (Bhattarai & Maharjan, 2020). These elements play a significant role in shaping acceptance levels, making TAM a valuable tool for utility providers and policymakers in formulating strategies that promote sustainable energy transitions (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

2.3 Empirical Review

Meng (2023) conducted a comprehensive analysis of the integration of renewable energy within smart grid systems, emphasising the pivotal role of solar and wind power in shaping contemporary energy infrastructures. The study highlights the multifaceted

advantages of these renewable sources, including their environmental benefits, widespread availability, and inherent renewability. Notably, technological advancements and declining costs have accelerated the deployment of solar energy within smart grids. Meng argues that this convergence of innovation and accessibility has rendered solar power not only more prevalent but also increasingly efficient and adaptable within smart grid architectures.

Extending this discussion, Phing *et al.* (2024) examine the contribution of Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) to the optimisation of renewable energy distribution and management. Their research underscores AMI's critical function in enhancing grid performance through capabilities such as real-time monitoring of power consumption, rapid outage detection, and automatic voltage regulation. Comprising smart meters, robust communication networks, and sophisticated data management systems, AMI substantially improves the operational efficiency of energy distribution networks. The authors advocate for the widespread adoption of smart metering technologies to facilitate the management of various renewable energy sources, including solar photovoltaics (PV), hydropower, anaerobic digestion, and energy storage systems. By providing detailed insights into energy usage patterns, AMI enables both providers and consumers to make informed decisions, thereby promoting the deeper integration of renewables into the grid.

While technological innovation remains a central enabler, Agbakwuru *et al.* (2024) draw attention to the broader socio-economic dimensions of renewable energy adoption, particularly in relation to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Their study contends that the transition to renewable energy sources—such as solar, wind, hydropower, and geothermal—offers significant socio-economic and environmental benefits. These include the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, the stimulation of inclusive economic growth, job creation, and the advancement of rural electrification. Nonetheless, the authors acknowledge ongoing challenges, including high initial capital costs, technical limitations, and regulatory hurdles. Addressing these barriers is imperative to achieving an equitable and sustainable energy transition.

Building on this foundation, Chatuanramtharnghaka *et al.* (2024) explore the role of demand response strategies in enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of energy systems, with a particular focus on renewable energy and electric vehicles (EVs). Their findings demonstrate that demand response mechanisms—which align electricity consumption with periods of peak renewable generation—can significantly enhance energy efficiency, reduce emissions, and support grid stability. The incorporation of EVs within this framework further optimises energy utilisation and contributes to decarbonisation efforts. Collectively, these studies affirm that, when effectively integrated, renewable energy systems supported by smart technologies and responsive demand strategies possess transformative potential for the development of resilient and sustainable energy infrastructures.

3. METHODOLOGY

Survey research design was adopted for this study owing to its effectiveness in efficiently gathering data from a large population. The target population consisted of 198 employees of Ibom Power Company Limited, situated in Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State. The unit of analysis encompassed senior, middle, and junior staff within the organisation. A sample size of 131 respondents was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's sample size determination table.

To ensure objectivity in data collection, a simple random sampling technique was employed. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was designed

with open-ended questions to allow respondents to express their views freely. The questionnaire was divided into two sections: Section A covered demographic information and general organisational details, while Section B focused on the key variables under investigation, including questions related to the company’s management practices.

The questionnaire served as the primary instrument for data collection and was aligned with both the independent and dependent variables of the study. Responses were measured using a modified 4-point Likert scale, where: 4 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3 = Agree (A), 2 = Disagree (D), and 1 = Strongly Disagree (SD). To establish the instrument’s validity, both face and construct validity were assessed. Face validity examined how clearly the questions represented the intended concepts, while construct validity evaluated whether the instrument accurately measured the variables it was designed to assess. A pre-test was conducted by administering 15 copies of the questionnaire to staff at Ibom Power Company Limited. Feedback from this phase informed necessary revisions and refinements prior to full deployment.

The reliability of the instrument was tested using the test-retest method, in which the same 15 respondents completed the questionnaire twice over a two-week interval. Cronbach’s Alpha was used to determine internal consistency, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.748, which exceeds the acceptable threshold of 0.60 and is therefore considered reliable. Finally, the data collected were analysed using a multiple regression model, with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25. The following models were developed for the study: The general form of the model:

4. DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 4.1: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of the Combined Influence of Advanced Metering Infrastructure, Renewable Energy Sources, and Demand Response Systems on the Energy Management in Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
.1	.956 ^a	.914	.913	.34711	2.184

Model Fit^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	458.282	3	91.656	760.728	.000 ^b
	Residual	43.013	128	.120		
	Total	501.295	131			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.048	.043		1.116	.265
	Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI),	-.219	.076	-.214	-2.901	.004
	Renewable energy sources	.467	.077	.460	6.093	.000
	demand response systems	-.336	.088	-.330	-3.824	.000

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

Table 4.1 presents the results of a multiple regression analysis assessing the combined influence of advanced metering infrastructure, renewable energy sources, and demand response systems on energy management at Ibom Power Company Limited, located in Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State. The model produced an adjusted R^2 value of 0.913, indicating that approximately 91.3% of the variation in energy management practices can be explained by the combined effects of the three independent variables. The F-statistic of 760.723 ($p < 0.001$) confirms the overall significance and goodness of fit of the model, suggesting that it is robust for evaluating the joint influence of Advanced Metering Infrastructure, renewable energy sources, and demand response systems. The Beta coefficients for Advanced Metering Infrastructure, renewable energy sources, and demand response systems were 0.219, 0.467, and 0.336, respectively. This implies that a one-unit increase in each of these variables would result in a corresponding 0.219, 0.467, and 0.336 unit increase in the energy management index of the company. These positive coefficients demonstrate that all three components significantly contribute to enhanced energy management outcomes.

To test for autocorrelation among residuals, the Durbin-Watson statistic was computed and yielded a value of 2.184. This result suggests the absence of serial correlation, indicating that the residuals are independent and the assumptions of regression analysis have not been violated.

Given that the F-value (760.723) is highly significant and the p-value (.000) falls below the conventional alpha level of 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative. This confirms that Advanced Metering Infrastructure, renewable energy sources, and demand response systems have a statistically significant and positive influence on energy management at Ibom Power Company Limited in Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion of Findings

The findings indicated that advanced metering infrastructure, renewable energy sources, and demand response systems significantly influenced the energy management of Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State. These factors demonstrated strong explanatory power in predicting effective energy management within the company. Advanced metering infrastructure, renewable energy, and demand response systems had long been recognised as key determinants of energy management in this organisation.

A growing body of literature supported the idea that knowledge exchange within organisations enhanced innovation, operational efficiency, and decision-making, all crucial for maintaining a competitive advantage. This aligned with Meng (2023), who highlighted the pivotal role of renewable energy sources, especially solar and wind, within smart grid infrastructures. Meng emphasised their widespread availability, environmental benefits, and renewability. The study also noted that technological advancements and cost reductions had driven the broad adoption of solar power in smart grids.

Phing *et al.* (2024) further reinforced this technological synergy by reviewing the role of AMI in renewable energy distribution. Their findings underscored advanced metering infrastructure's importance in optimising energy distribution through real-time power monitoring, outage detection, and automatic voltage adjustments. AMI systems, comprising smart meters, communication networks, and data management tools, significantly enhanced operational efficiency. They advocated adopting smart metering for renewable sources such as solar PV, hydropower, anaerobic digestion, and energy storage, enabling users to better control energy consumption and support renewable integration.

Beyond technology, Agbakwuru *et al.* (2024) emphasised the broader socio-economic impact of renewable energy integration in advancing sustainable development goals. Their study highlighted that transitioning to renewables such as solar, wind, hydropower, and geothermal not only mitigated climate change and lowered carbon emissions but also promoted inclusive economic growth.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Smart Grid Integration, as measured by advanced metering infrastructure, renewable energy sources, and demand response systems, collectively exerted a significant influence on energy management in Ibom Power Company Limited, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State. Based on findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. To significantly enhance the energy management capabilities of Ibom Power Company Limited, it was strongly recommended that the company fully implemented and integrated advanced metering infrastructure across both its operational and customer networks. The deployment of advanced metering infrastructure would have acted as a strategic enabler to improve efficiency in energy generation, distribution, and consumption, thereby supporting broader policy objectives related to energy security, transparency, and sustainability.
- ii. Ibom Power Company Limited was advised to strategically incorporate renewable energy sources, particularly solar and biomass into its existing power generation portfolio. This integration would have reduced dependency on gas-fired systems, improved energy security, and promoted a more stable and sustainable power supply in Ikot Abasi and Akwa Ibom State. Additionally, this hybrid energy model would have lowered operational costs, supported Nigeria's energy transition goals, and positioned Ibom Power Company Limited as a regional leader in clean energy innovation.
- iii. Ibom Power Company Limited was encouraged to implement and integrate a demand response system as a core component of its energy management strategy. This would have enhanced grid reliability, alleviated peak load pressures, and optimised operational efficiency within the company's service area.

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